

“INDIA AT 77”-Navigating an Emerging Economy Amidst Reforms

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Abstract India stands at a crucial juncture in its economic trajectory, marked by the simultaneous challenges and opportunities posed by globalization and climate change. India's economic progress has been nothing short of extraordinary. Its GDP has risen throughout the years to become the world's third-largest economy. A young and lively workforce, a growing middle class, and a quickly expanding internet infrastructure have all contributed to the country's precipitous rise. With the rise of varied industries such as information technology, pharmaceuticals, manufacturing, and agriculture, India's economic variety serves as a buffer against global instabilities. The approach centers on utilizing data and statistics from relevant secondary sources to tackle the article's subject matter. It underscores the importance of the current political, economic, and social landscape in shaping the discussion.

Keywords GDP In Different Sectors, LPG Reforms, Make In India, Start Up.

Introduction India is one of the largest economies in the world, and perhaps, one of the most prominent emerging markets as well. This paper examines the current state of India in terms of strategy, mindset and its implications on economy and other determinants that impede growth. India, at 77 years of independence, has undergone significant transformation in various sectors. Agricultural Sector in India has moved from Green Revolution to crop diversification, from government policies to organic farming and what not .The focus on sustainability, technological adoption, and policy reforms will be crucial in ensuring the sector's resilience and growth in the coming years. On the other hand India has moved from a closed door policy to an open door policy starting from 1991; greatly affecting our next two sectors. In the manufacturing sector, from 1991 onwards, we have focused more on foreign direct investments but for a balanced economy we have started initiatives like 'Make in India'. The focus on sustainability, digital transformation, and infrastructure development will be crucial in shaping the future of the industrial landscape. Moving onto the next sector i.e. Service sector , IT services have been a blessing for our economy There's a huge development in service sector be it in the education or health sector or be it in the infrastructure or E-Commerce sector, service sector has seen it all. The focus on innovation, skill development, and policy reforms will be crucial in sustaining this growth and addressing existing challenges.

Objective of study

1. To examine the progress of Indian economy among the ongoing reforms.
2. To present a comprehensive analysis of the interplay between different sectors in India's growth narrative.
3. To understand the role of government policies and initiatives.

Review of Literature

India is an emerging global economy. The views of Hogg (2007) has been expressed that when we glance at the potential of India, categorically, it has a substantial platform to

capitalize its resources and transfigure as an economic power house, but the road to success is highly reliant on relationships with its neighborhood, that will become the inflection point for any country looking to grow and progress India is an emerging global economy. The views of Hogg (2007) has been expressed that when we glance at the potential of India, categorically, it has a substantial platform to capitalize its resources and transfigure as an economic power house, but the road to success is highly reliant on relationships with its neighborhood, that will become the inflection point for any country looking to grow and progress India is an emerging global economy. The views of Hogg (2007) has been expressed that when we glance at the potential of India, categorically, it has a substantial platform to capitalize its resources and transfigure as an economic power house, but the road to success is highly reliant on relationships with its neighborhood, that will become the inflection point for any country looking to grow and progress.

According to Datta. S, Prashant Kumar Singh and Rumel Dahiya (2012), are the neighborhood and relationships with them. India, sharing border with the second largest economy, which has gone through skyrocketing growth and attracted majority investor to have an eye on opportunities underlying in China. While examining the relationship of India with China, one would clearly identify the relationship being contentious due to dominance in region and few other concerns that encompass territory issues and military dominance. Moreover, the mounting collaboration of China with Pakistan and Bangladesh has also led wariness and austerity amid China and India's fragile relationship.

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Chauduri (2002) also reported that the "expectations of rapid and sustained growth of output and employment ...have not materialized." The author concluded that value added growth in the 1990s was inferior to that in the 1980s, that the industrial base had become shallower, that employment growth in the 1990s was negative in five out of nine years and that the labour productivity stagnated after 1995/96, after having increased 4 in the early 1990s. Here again no attention is paid to the changes in protection, prices and costs that resulted from the reforms.

A much more positive picture was drawn by Panagariya (2004), who argued that growth in the 1990s was more robust than that of the 1980s and that it was achieved through important policy changes. The main policy changes held responsible for accelerated growth are the liberalization of foreign trade, the reduction in industrial licencing and opening to foreign direct investment.

Main Text

India's Journey through Our Eyes (1947- 2024)

India's economic growth is a result of policies and initiatives adopted by the Indian government. After independence, Britishers left India with a crumbled economy. But as soon as Indian government was elected it shifted its focus on Agriculture Development primarily. Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru's development model envisaged a dominant role of the state as an all-pervasive entrepreneur and financier of private businesses. India set up the Planning Commission in 1950 to oversee the entire range of planning, including resource allocation, implementation and appraisal of five-year plans. The five-year plans were centralized economic and social growth programmes. Five year plans appeared really effective but lacked the required implementation. Population of India in the consecutive years suddenly rose so did the poor population. In 1964, the war with China had exposed India's economic weakness. Chronic food shortages and price rise convinced the then PM Lal Bahadur Shastri that India needed to move away from centralized planning and price controls. 1960's marked the era of the green revolution which resulted in the adoption of modern farming techniques. Addressing the poor population of the country, Indira Gandhi launched "Gareebi Hatao" programme Global partnership in the manufacturing sector was initiated by the collaboration of Maruti with Japanese car manufacturing company Suzuki in 1983.

Following this, Indian economy was finally opened in 1991's economic LPG reforms. This came out to be a significant step resulting in many Multinational companies setting up their offices in India boosting the tertiary sector of India. Following years marked the development of tertiary sector and reduced dependence on agriculture making the tertiary sector the majority contributor in India's economy. In 2005 government introduced MGNREGA Scheme to provide employment to people. The adequate use of opportunities for the demographic dividend can prove to be a cornerstone in India's journey of

becoming 'Viksit Bharat'. Over time several other schemes have been introduced to boost India's economy and shape India in becoming a global economy power.

The following page consists of tables that offer a comparative look of all the three sectors of the economy in two time frames and the various policies and reforms initiated by the government in various sectors for the upliftment and overall growth of the Indian economy. The following data has been taken from various authentic sources and NCERT textbooks.

1945-1990

Sectors of Economy	People Employed	Contribution To GDP	Growth Rate
PRIMARY	71%	40%	54%
Major Policies and Programs -First few five year plans, green revolution, subsidies, abolition of Zamindari system			
SECONDARY	11%	10%	16%
Major policies and programs -Government made many plans for the promotion of small scale and handicrafts industry. Government opted for labour intensive production to provide employment to people).			
TERTIARY	18%	50%	30%
Major policies and programs - Major medical and engineering institutes were set up to facilitate higher education and skill development (AIIMS, IIT, IIM etc.)			

1991-2024

Sectors of Economy	People Employed	Contribution To GDP	Growth Rate
PRIMARY	44%	12%	15.4%
Major policies and programs Pradhan mantri kisan yojna , Pradhan mantri jan dhan yojna			
SECONDARY	25%	20%	31.6%
Major policies and programs -Startup India , Atamnirbhar Bharat , Make In India etc.			
TERTIARY	31%	68%	53%
Major policies and programs Emergence of MNCs , LPG reforms , Foreign Direct Investment in IT Industry, Digital India Programme, Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana etc.			

Make In India

The make in India initiative was launched by Prime Minister in September 2014. It was devised to transform India into a global design and manufacturing hub. It was launched against the backdrop of the crisis in 2013. The Make in India initiative is based on four pillars, which have been identified to give boost to entrepreneurship in India, not only in manufacturing but also other sectors for the next three years, aimed at raising the contribution of the manufacturing sector to 25% of the GDP in the coming years. It aims at raising the contribution of the manufacturing sector to 25% of the GDP in the coming years.

Benefits Of Make In India

Millions of jobs have been created across various sectors. For instance, the "Make in India" initiative has contributed to the creation of over 10 million direct jobs by 2023. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has seen record inflows, with India receiving \$85 billion in 2023. The GDP has grown from around 16% in 2014 to approximately 19% by 2023.

There were many other schemes to facilitate make in India programme such as: Startup India, Digital India, Skill India mission etc.

Startup India

Startup India scheme is an important government scheme that was launched on 16th January 2016 with an aim to promote and support the start-ups in India by providing bank finances. The Startup India scheme is based majorly on three pillars which are mentioned below:

1. Providing funding support and incentives to the various start-ups of the country.
2. To provide Industry-Academia Partnership & Incubation.
3. Simplification and Handholding.

The below are the benefits and advancements of 'Startup India'.

